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Technical Report · July 2025

DOI: 10.13140/RG.2.2.23381.54244

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A categorical characterization of relative entropy on arbitrary measurable spaces

Remark on the paper of Gagne and Panangaden

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A categorical characterization of relative entropy on standard Borel spaces
[https://doi.org/10.46298/lmcs-19\(4:10\)2023](https://doi.org/10.46298/lmcs-19(4:10)2023)

The above paper gives a categorical characterization of the relative entropy on standard Borel spaces. Note that here, a categorical characterization of the relative entropy on any measurable space is given.

The reason they limited it to standard Borel spaces is because they require the existence of a regular conditional probability measure. However, in fact, they use the existence of a regular conditional probability measure when the sub σ -algebra is a finite partition. Therefore, the assumption of a standard Borel space is completely unnecessary. Specifically, this is the proof of Theorem 5.3. For each n , p_n^* is a simple function, so the corresponding partition is a finite partition and the existence of a regular conditional probability measure (disintegration) is trivial.